

COVID-19 Bibliometrics 15th – 21st February 2021

www.covid19bibliometrics.org

A. Medicine and Health

March 19, 2020 (Eur. Radiol)

Chest CT manifestations of new coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19): a pictorial review.

Ye, Z., Zhang, Y., Wang, Y. *et al*

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00330-020-06801-0>

The authors perform a literature review and summarize the typical and relatively atypical CT manifestations in COVID-19. They found that ground glass opacities, consolidation, reticular pattern and crazy paving pattern are typical CT manifestations of COVID-19. Emerging atypical CT manifestations include airway changes, pleural changes and fibrosis were demonstrated in COVID-19 patients. They conclude that CT manifestations may associate with the progression and prognosis of COVID-19.

February 19, 2021 (JAMA Inf Dis)

Sequelae in Adults at 6 Months After COVID-19 Infection

Jennifer K. Logue, Nicholas M. Franko, Denise J. McCulloch

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2021.0830>

This cohort study analysed persistent symptoms among adults with coronavirus disease 2019 up to 9 months after illness onset. They found that the most common persistent symptoms were fatigue and anosmia or ageusia.

February 18, 2021 (JAMA Psychiatry)

Posttraumatic Stress Disorder in Patients after Severe COVID-19 Infection

Delfina Janiri, Angelo Carfi, Gerogios D. Kotzalidis *et al*.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapsychiatry.2021.0109>

This cross-sectional study analyzes characteristics associated with posttraumatic stress disorder in patients after severe coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19).

February 12, 2021 (Science)

Structure-guided multivalent nanobodies block SARS-CoV-2 infection and suppress mutational escape

Paul-Alber Koenig, Hrishikesh Das, Hejun Liu *et al*.

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abe6230>

Nanobodies are single-domain antibodies that have the potential to be administered by inhalation. Koenig et al. describe four nanobodies that bind to the SARS-CoV2 spike protein and prevent infection of cells

February 11, 2021 (The NEJM)

Antibody Status and Incidence of SARS-CoV-2 Infection in Health Care Workers

Sheila F. Lumley, Denise O'Donnell, Nicole E. Stoesser et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa2034545>

The authors investigated the incidence of PCR confirmed SARS-CoV2 infection in seropositive and seronegative health care workers attending testing of asymptomatic and symptomatic staff in United Kingdom. They found that the presence of anti-spike or anti-nucleocapsid igG antibodies was associated with a substantially reduced risk of SARS-CoV2 reinfection in the ensuing 6 months.

December 28, 2020 (PLOS ONE)

Factors associated with psychological distress during the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic on the predominantly general population: A systematic review and meta-analysis

Yeli Wang, Monica Palanichamy Kala, Tazeen H. Jafar

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0244630>

The authors analysed 68 publications involving 288, 830 participants from 19 countries to determine the factors associated with anxiety and depression during the COVID-19 pandemic. They found that 1 in 3 adults had COVID-19 related psychological distress, affecting more women than men. They also found that urban-rural living and socioeconomic factors were significantly associated with psychological distress

B. Science and Engineering

February 25, 2021 (Journal of Environmental Sciences)

Impact of meteorological condition changes on air quality and particulate chemical composition during the COVID-19 lockdown

Jing Ding, Qili Dai, Yafei Li et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jes.2021.02.022>

This study is about the stringent quarantine measures during the COVID-19 lockdown period (January 23, 2020 to March 15, 2020) that have resulted in a distinct decrease in anthropogenic source emissions in North China Plain compared to the paralleled period of 2019. They also studies the influence of humidity and weather condition.

February 22, 2021 (Procedia Computer Science)

COVID-19 Time Series Prediction

Leonardo Sestrem de Oliveira, Sarah Beatriz Gruetzmacher, Joao Paulo Teixeira.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2021.01.254>

In this work, the ANN is applied in predicting the number of COVID-19 confirmed cases and deaths and also the future seven days for the time series of Brazil, Portugal and the United States. From the simulations the authors conclude that the prediction of confirmed cases and deaths from COVID-19 have been successfully made by the ANN. Overall, the ANN with a specific test set had a Mean Squared Error (MSE) of 50% higher than the ANN with a random test set.

February 9, 2021 (Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease)

Change in outbreak epicentre and its impact on the importation risks of COVID-19 progression: A modelling study

Oyelola A. Adegboye, Adeshina I. Adekunle, Anton Pak et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmaid.2021.101988>

This study explores early assessment of the influence of spatial proximities and travel patterns from Italy on the further spread of SARS-CoV-2 worldwide. Using data on the number of confirmed cases of COVID-19 and air travel data between countries, they applied a stochastic meta-population model to estimate the global spread of COVID-19. They found significant negative association between disease arrival time and number of cases imported from Italy ($r = -0.43$, $p = 0.004$) and significant positive association between the number of COVID-19 cases and daily travel influx from Italy ($r = 0.39$, $p = 0.011$). They concluded that the epicentre changes affect the dynamics of SARS-CoV-2 spread change.

C. Social Sciences, Humanity and Public Policy

February 11, 2021 (Journal of Business Research)

The effect of COVID – 19 pandemic on global stock market volatility: Can economic strength help to manage the uncertainty?

Moshfique Uddin, Anup Chowdhury, Keith Anderson et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.01.061>

This paper examines the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on stock market volatility and whether economic strength can potentially mitigate the possible detrimental effect of the global pandemic on stock market volatility.

A set of selected country-level economic characteristics and factors such as economic resilience, intensity of capitalism, level of corporate governance, financial development, monetary policy rate and quality of health system, are discussed.

Using data from 34 developed and emerging markets, it is found that these country-level economic characteristics and factors do help to reduce the volatility arising due to the virus pandemic.

February 4, 2021 (Research in International Business and Finance)

Innovation as recovery strategy for SMEs in emerging economies during the COVID-19 pandemic

Santiago-Omar Caballero-Morales.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ribaf.2021.101396>

Innovation is identified as a key aspect of business recovery in the ongoing and post-COVID-19 pandemic period. This work presents a multidisciplinary methodological approach to guide small to medium enterprises how to innovate their products for new markets and making a better use of their limited available resources. A case study example indicates that the use of digital resources is the main facilitator for networking and research-based design of innovative products within the context of “social distancing”.

January 19, 2021 (Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management)

The COVID-19 pandemic and organisational learning for disaster planning and management: A perspective of tourism businesses from a destination prone to consecutive disasters

Gde Indra Bhaskara & Viachaslau Filimonau.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2021.01.011>

This paper evaluates the effect of past disasters on organisational learning of tourism businesses in Bali. It finds that limited human and social capital restricts their organisational learning, exposing vulnerability of the Balinese tourism industry to future disastrous events. The authors conclude that stakeholder capacity building exercises are required to enhance disaster resilience of tourism businesses and their host destination.

January 11, 2021 (European Management Journal)

At the boundary: Post-COVID agenda for business and management research in Europe and beyond

Thomas Boysen Anker.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emj.2021.01.003>

A rapidly growing body of scholarly research discusses the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on business and management research. This Reflection on Europe takes stock of the situation and reflects critically on the deeper changes to the business ecosystem which the pandemic may engender. Based on surface level observations in three different contexts of business research, the analysis uncovers changes to underlying market circumstances which point towards radical shifts in the boundary conditions between business and society. The article concludes with suggestions for a post-COVID research agenda.